

CHAPTER-IV

ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF TOURISM INDUSTRY IN INDIA

”The tourism sector is a source of wealth and employment, it is a tool for social cohesion, for the consolidation of the population, for fighting against climate change and inequality; It is an accelerator in the achievement of the SDGs and digital transformation.”

HRH King Felipe VI (2020)

This chapter is based on the secondary data regarding tourism policies of States, foreign exchange, employment, foreign tourist arrival trends and government initiatives with regards to tourism.

The tourism sector in India is on boom and it will flourish because of its unearthed tourism product although Corona Virus Disease 19 (COVID-19) has almost destroyed the tourism industry for months. But no doubt tourism is dynamic and this pandemic outbreak has again proved it. The Ministry of Tourism is National Tourism Organisation (NTO) or apex body with regards to tourism in the country. This organisation cooperates among Central, States, Union Territories Government and other stakeholders of tourism industry to provide a common platform for tourism education, product development, marketing and promotion of tourism products, research and development, issues travel advisory, investment facilitation, international cooperation and more. The ministry of tourism has paramount role in Indian tourism industry and vice versa. According to Tourism Satellite Account India (2006), the acceptance to tour has increased because of its employment generation capability either directly or indirectly. Tourism has ability to provide employment to subject experts, skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled human resources. In addition tourism has multi-dimensional role in Indian economy and nation as a whole through foreign exchange, foreign investment, destination development, infrastructure development, community development and sustainable practices. In 2002-2003 Indian tourism share (direct) in global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) was 2.78 percent (8th rank) and in context of employment share (direct) was 4.57 % and ranked 3rd highest (Tourism Satellite Account: India, 2006).

The Incredible India Tourist Facilitator (IITF, 2020) Certification Programme has defined the tourism as an activity which start, as someone step out from home with a purpose (for holiday, business, Visiting Friends and Relatives, medical treatment etc.) but for more than one day and less than 365 days.

Image 4.1: Tourism

Source: iitf

4.1 A Glance at Indian Tourism Industry

India ranked at 65th in 2013 and it was improved to rank 34th in 2019 as per the World Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index (WTTCI, 2019) of World Economic Forum. The Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTAs) during the period January-November 2019 were 9669633 as compared to 9366478 in January- November 2018 registering a growth of 3.2%. According to Ministry of Tourism, Government of India, Indian tourism industry had achieved a landmark in 2017, with the number of foreign tourist arrivals crossing the 10 million for the first time in India’s tourism history, and earned foreign exchange worth \$27.3 billion, an increase of 19.1 per cent over corresponding earnings in 2016. In 2019 global tourism as well as Indian tourism industry has performed remarkably in context of employment generation, economic development and growth in tourism industry. The tourism industry is highly dynamic and it can be analysed from below mentioned table 4.1.

Table 4.1: World and Indian Tourism Versus Covid-19 Impact on Tourism

Pre-Covid-19		Post-Covid-19 (projected for 2020)	
World Tourism (2019) *	Indian Tourism(2019) *	World Tourism *	Indian Tourism **
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10.3% contribution to Global GDP. • 4th largest contributor to global economy. • 330 million jobs • 1 in 4 new jobs created by travel and tourism industry • 3.5 % growth rate of global travel and tourism industry against 2.5 % of global economic growth. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6.8% contribution to Indian GDP. • 8% of total employment • 39821800 jobs. • Largest share of inbound arrivals from Bangladesh (12%) • Largest outbound departure to UAE (13%) • Spending-Leisure (94%), Business (6%) • Spending-Domestic (83%), International (17%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100-120 million direct jobs at risk. • USD 910 –USD 1.2 trillion loss in exports • 850 million to 1.1 billion number of less international tourists. • 60%-80% drop in international tourists. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 35-40 million jobs • ₹ 5 trillion revenue loss.

Source: *WTTC, **FICCI.

According to India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF, 2020), the demand for indian tourism product and servicices is growing year by year, the niche tourism will provide more employment opportunities, policies are favouring the tourism business and India hosts diverse floara, fauna andculture. It can be infered that because of myriad of opportunities for tourism product developemnt, India can be promoted in international market as ‘One visa-36 countries’.

IBEF ads that the government of India is working to achieve one per cent share in global international tourist arrivals by 2020 and 2 per cent share by 2025.

- Under Budget 2020-21, the Government of India allotted Rs 1,200 crore (US\$ 171.70 million) for development of tourist circuits under Swadesh Darshan for eight north-eastern states.
- In 2019, government reduced GST on hotel rooms with tariffs of Rs 1,001 (US\$ 14.32) to Rs 7,500 (US\$ 107.31) per night to 12 per cent; those above Rs 7,501 (US\$ 107.32) to 18 per cent to increase India’s competitiveness as a tourism destination’.

No doubts, that government is desperate to integrate infrastructure development along with the benefits of tourism. With the rise in international tourist arrival, there will be demand for quality human resources in tourism industry.

Image 4.2: Advantages of tourism in India

Source: IBEF (2020)

4.2 Indian Context of understanding Tourism

The Ministry of Tourism, Government of India (2015), discerns that “Travel and Tourism is a mirror of our evolving world. Reflecting economic, social and environmental shifts in our times, the Tourism sector is a dynamic, inspiring force, clearly mapping how nations are advancing as individual societies and economies, as well as members of the global community. Because of its dynamic nature, a nation’s tourism sector requires constant monitoring and understanding to ensure it is being leveraged for the greater good of the people of the destination, and as a competitive force on the global landscape. This is especially true for nations looking to the tourism sector as a vehicle for national growth, development and employment generation.” The ministry has explained that first National Tourism was formulated in 1982. Policy on Tourism for India was first formulated in 1982. The role policy was to inform the nation about the importance of tourism industry. It was a way to find out the challenges for Indian tourism industry and opportunities available for country during that closed economy and licence-raj.

Historically, Indian tourism industry had poor performance at global platform and it is because of ‘same tourism policy for decades’. It shows the incompetence of

national tourism planning or Ministry of Tourism. The second national tourism policy came into practice in 2002 after a gap of almost 20 years. Although first tourism policy of ministry had accepted in that tourism is an important industry. The policy was aimed to use tourism as a tool for national economic development. The employment generation and poverty eradication were the major aims through sustainable practices. This policy recognised the importance of domestic tourism and public-private partnership for tourism development. Besides it the policy explored seven key points to boost national image and consequently tourism development in the country. The points are as follow: Swagat (welcome), Soochana (information), Suvidha (facilitation), Suraksha (safety), Sahyog (cooperation), Samrachana (infrastructure development) and Safai (cleanliness). Even the research by Fazili et al. (2018), has shown the “fact that tourism development is predominantly the result (in sequence) of Safety (Suraksha), Cooperation (Sahyog) factor, Welcome (Swagat), Cleanliness (Safai), Facilitation (Suvidha), Infrastructure (Samrachna) and Information (Soochna) factors”(pp. 346).The five key goals of the national tourism policy 2002 was positioning tourism as national priority (Tourism satellite account, coordination among tourism stakeholders, tourism in concurrent list of Indian constitution), global competitiveness of India as a tourism destination (e-Visa, opening up Indian sky, tourism police), world class infrastructure (huge investment by ministry og tourism in ports, airports, roads, basic facilities and urban infrastructure), revamping the existing tourism product and new market for Indian tourism products(more form of alternative tourism) as well as sustainable development plans. The national tourism policy 2002 has beautifully tried to embrace/engulf the mind of tourists either foreign or domestic through the following lines.

“Atithi Devo Bhava

Guest is god

India is a journey of mind and soul

It is a journey of five senses

It is a journey of self-discovery

It is a journey of self-fulfilment”

Source: Ministry of Tourism (National Tourism Policy, 2002).

The religious tourism has an important role in Indian economy. The Maha Kumbh Mela held in 2013 had seen 7.86 crore pilgrims, including 3.50 lakh foreign

tourists, and a record over 24 crore people visited Kumbh-2019, more than total tourists in Uttar Pradesh in 2014-17. The Kumbh 2019 visitors included 10.30 lakh foreign tourists. It shows that foreign tourists are magnetised towards Indian culture. Also, during the 49-days Kumbh Mela 2019 that concluded in March, a significant 24.01 crore people visited the Sangam city (Hindustan Times, 2019). The religious tourism can be used as a Soft Power to strengthen India's outreach to Southeast Asia (Bhonsle, 2019).

4.3 Tourism Planning in India

The hospitality education started in 1954 at Institute of hotel management Mumbai (2019) while tourism education started in 1972 at College of Vocational Studies, Delhi University (CVS, 2017). The tourism was recognised as an industry in June 1982 and the recognition agency was Niti Aayog, the then Planning Commission of India. In July, 1986 the Planning Commission of India set up the National Committee on Tourism in order to formulate plans for the tourism sector under the chairmanship of Mohammed Yunus (Dayananda and Leelavathi, 2016).

According to Livemint (2019), the Government of India in 2019 has propelled the Indian tourism industry through opening up 137 mountain peaks for adventure tourism. Some of the peaks include Kanchenjunga (8598 Mt) and Nepal Peak (7168 Mt) in Sikkim, Garur Parbat (6,504 Mt) and Purbi Dunagiri (6,489 Mt) in Uttarakhand, and Mulkila (6,517 Mt) in Himachal Pradesh. The majority of the peaks are located in Uttarakhand (51) and Himachal Pradesh (47) while the rest are located in Sikkim (24), Jammu and Kashmir and Ladakh. These steps will definitely attract the adventure tourists and consequently employment, infrastructure and financial benefit to the national economy as well as hill states of the country. The government has extended the e-visa time period from one year to five years and reduction of visa fee from \$25 to \$10 dollars during the peak season (PIB, 2020).

The government's initiatives of incorporating a planned tourism sector in India went a long way in boosting Indian tourism. In May, 1992 the National Action Plan for tourism was announced. The major objectives of the plans were; to boost domestic tourism, to develop the tourist circuits, attract International tourists, growth in global tourism share and Employment generation through tourism. The seventh five year plan India (1985-1989) has played a significant role in Indian tourism growth

planning. It was planned to promote domestic tourism more effectively, promotion of beach, adventure and winter sports tourism through infrastructure development. During the eighth five year plan (1992- 1997) the private sector was asked to invest in tourism industry and infrastructure development for the alternative forms of tourism was on agenda (Dayananda and Leelavathi, 2016).

According to Press Information Bureau (2019), Tourism sector is a major engine of economic growth that contributes significantly in terms of GDP, foreign exchange earnings and employment. In India, the Tourism sector had been performing well with Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTAs) growing at 14 per cent to 10.4 million and Foreign Exchange Earnings (FEEs) at 20.6 per cent to US\$28.7 billion in 2017-18. The growth of inbound tourism can be accredited to few of the reasons e.g. rise in world heritage sites, growing infrastructure facilities, easy e-visa and extension. However, the sector witnessed a slowdown in 2018-19. The Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTA) in 2018-19 stood at 10.6 million compared to 10.4 million in 2017-18. The growth rate of FTAs declined from 14.2 per cent in 2017-18 to 2.1 per cent in 2018-19. Foreign Exchange Earnings (FEEs) from tourism stood at US\$27.7 billion in 2018-19 as compared to US 28.7 billion in 2017-18. The FEEs declined from 20.6 per cent in 2017-18 to -3.3 per cent in 2018-19. Outbound tourism increased in recent years, with the number of departures of Indian nationals from India that stood at 23.94 million in 2017 as against 21.87 million in 2016 with a growth rate of 9.5 per cent in 2017. This was more than double the foreign tourist arrivals in India.

According to the government of India (2019), Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, Skill India Program and Make in India program are the flagship schemes of government of India which are described below. These schemes have been implementing and working along the aim of tapping the potential of tourism for job creation, economic development and exploring the horizon of Indian tourism industry.

a) Swadesh Darshan and Tourism

The tourism industry is a major tool for infrastructure development across the country. It has witnessed that tourism is bringing the positive change in the country in context of infrastructure development i.e. it is a Central Government sponsored scheme launched in 2014-2015 and it was supposed to complete by March 2020. Under Swadesh Darshan scheme there are 15 proposed major theme based tourism

circuits to develop across the country. The Ministry of Tourism has defined the tourist circuit' under Swadesh Darshan scheme as 'a route having at least three major tourist destinations which are distinct and apart. It also includes the things as follow:

- Circuits should have well defined entry and exit points.
- A tourist who enters should get motivated to visit most of the places identified in the circuit.
- A Circuit could be confined to a State or could be a regional circuit covering more than one State/Union Territory.
- These circuits may have one dominant theme and other sub-themes.

There are 15 major themes under the Swadesh Darshan project, are being developed i.e. Ecotourism, Wildlife, Buddhist, Desert, Spiritual, Ramayana, Krishna, Coastal, Northeast, Rural, Himalayan, Tribal, Sufi, Tirthanka, and Heritage Circuits (Swadeshdarshan, 2019). The employment generation, infrastructure development, promotion of alternative forms of tourism and diversification of the Indian tourism products are the major reasons for the scheme.

b) Conservation and Promotion of Heritage, Culture and Spirituality and Tourism

The National Mission on Pilgrimage Rejuvenation and Spiritual, Heritage Augmentation Drive is promoting tourism and developing tourism products across the country. Consequently it is also leading to the Conservation and promotion of heritage, culture and spirituality. The tourism marketing is spreading the traditions and practices of India at origin of the tourists. Pilgrimage based tourists destinations are being developed under 'National Mission on Pilgrimage Rejuvenation and Spiritual, Heritage Augmentation Drive' (PRASHAD) Scheme. A total number of 28 projects have been sanctioned till January, 2020 for an amount of Rs.840.02Crore under PRASHAD scheme (Press Information Bureau, 2020).

c) Adopt a Heritage Project and Tourism

It is a joint project of Ministry of Tourism, Ministry of Culture and Archaeological Survey of India, State(s) and UT(s) Government. The project is dedicated to the development of heritage sites and tourist sites in context of 'tourist friendly'. The Ministry of Tourism has signed 27 memoranda of understanding

(MoU's) till January 2020 under the Adopt a Heritage project (Press Information Bureau, 2020).

d) Liberalisation towards International Tourism

Tourism has liberalised the entry of foreign tourists in India. The e-visa scheme has extended to 169 countries. Indian borders are open to enter foreign tourists through e-visa at 28 airports and 5 seaports. It is issued under e-Tourist visa, e-Business Visa, e-Medical Visa and e-Medical Attendant Visa.

- i) e-Tourist Visa duration extended from one year to 5 year. It will include stay stipulation of maximum of 90 days, multiple entry and non-extendable.
- ii) This e-Tourist Visa for 5 years will be with one-month e-Tourist Visa with double entry, has been launched. The e-Conference Visa and e-Conference Visa for Government, Public sector Units, conferences, would be provided for private conferences organized by private persons/companies/ organizations (Press Information Bureau, 2020).

e) National Tourism Policy Draft-2015

It is proposed to align National tourism policy draft-2015 with UNWTO i.e. practising the global code of ethics and achieving sustainable tourism goal through tourism. The Ministry accepts that “The growth of the tourism sector will have a direct and tangible impact on the Indian economy in terms of spreading benefits across the country including remote areas and providing employment and entrepreneurial opportunities to youth, women, marginalized sections of the society and those in the informal sector”. It can be asserted that tourism can take its benefits to the remotest of the remote area in the country. The ministry has accepted that tourism can help India to fight climate change, eradication of unemployment and poverty as well as women empowerment. Policy argued that there is need to strengthen Public – Private – People Participation (PPPP) framework for holistic development of tourism. One of the major objectives of the policy is ‘Increase India’s share in world tourist arrivals from the present 0.68% to 1% by 2020 and increase to 2% by 2025’. Unfortunately, COVID-19 has washed away or delayed to achieve this objective to achieve. As Economic Times (2020) reported that “in February 2020, 1.01 million foreign tourists arrived in India compared to 1.08 million in February

2019, registering a year-on-year decrease of 6.6 per cent already”. This fall in foreign tourists arrival will rise as peak tourist season is July-March (Times of India, 2019). In Addition, Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry (FICCI, 2020) has stated that “Crippled by the coronavirus pandemic, India’s travel and hospitality industry are staring at a loss of ₹ 5 trillion of revenues during the next year and more than 35-40 million jobs are now in jeopardy, indirect and direct both”. This policy has proposed to establish a ‘national tourism university’ with an aim to research and development, consultancy, skilling of community and to make a paradigm shift from ‘job seeker to job creator’ i.e. is incorporation of entrepreneurial skills among tourism graduates as well as diversification of Indian tourism products.

f) Make in India Program and Tourism

It was formally introduced by the government of India in September 25, 2014. It was proposed to bring transparency, responsibility and accountability of the government. The main idea was to provide employment opportunities, putting national human resource talent into innovation and ease of doing business in the country. There are 25 sectors which are taken into account to stimulate national economy as tourism sector is one of them (IBEF, 2019).

g) National Mission on Cultural Mapping and Tourism

The National Mission on Cultural Mapping (NMCM) has been set up by the Ministry of Culture in 2017. It is a repository of data, collected from art and culture academies of the Ministry of Culture. It will represent the data in digital form regarding artists, art forms and geo location with inputs from Central Ministries, State Governments, Union Territories, and art and culture bodies. The technology will come from of National E-Governance Division (NEGD)/Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MEITY). According to Assumma and Ventura (2014), “Cultural mapping consists in an innovative tool of knowledge, utilized in the local development processes to enhance territorial resources and to increase local growth in terms of environmental, social and economic sustainability”. It leads to sustainable cultural tourism development, change tourist behaviour, community development and collaboration between local governance and national tourism policy makers. It can be inferred that cultural mapping is used as an innovative tool for cultural and heritage

tourism development and landmark initiative to generate employment for local community and growth of national economy.

h) Project Sagarmala and Tourism

As per the Sagarmala initiative, the Government of India plans to develop six new ports across five coastal States of India. 189 projects with a projected cost of USD 21 Billion have been identified India have 72 coastal districts and have 18% of total population through Sagarmala project. Besides the development of ports, this work for the skilling of the communities in various sector. The human resource is being produced/skilled for employment through tourism development in the coastal region of the country.

i) Tourism among top Priorities in Indian States

It is found through the analyses of different State Tourism Policies that employment generation and economic development are the key motives to adopt tourism industry in the States across the country. It is also found that States are desperate to build more infrastructure than past to have a bigger share of national tourism i.e. domestic and foreign tourists. The States like Kerala, Sikkim, Madhya Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh are near to achieve the sustainable development through tourism policies. The states are trying to promote the respective State as Global brand in tourism industry.

Andhra Pradesh is blessed with the pristine beaches, sacred places of worship, lush green forests, spicy cuisine and hospitable people are attracting the tourists to the State. The domestic tourists arrival was 195.8 million and foreign tourists arrival was .23 million in 2019 (IBEF, 2020).

Assam through State Tourism Policy 2017 under the light of the policy promoting State as global brand through promoting the State as ‘awesome Assam’ to attract the domestic and international tourists. The State of Assam is promoting eco-tourism, river cruise tourism, infrastructure development and beautification of historical places. Whereas, Bihar is promoting education, cultural tourism and religious tourism. The development of knowledge and religious hubs will attract 1 lakh tourists per year by 2020. Chhattisgarh has a plan to promote religious adventure and heritage tourism by 2022 through government vision-2022 for the state. While

Goa has already a big known destination across the globe. Tourism industry is among top 3 contributor towards State GDP. Goa is tourist Paradise because of its natural scenery unique beaches and cultural diversity. Gujarat is also desperate to develop the tourist infrastructure and to make it a global tourist destination. Government is working through government vision 2020.

Tourism industry in Himachal Pradesh flourished in mid 80s and 90s. At present tourism has become a major tool for foreign exchange earnings and employment generation. The State has promoted from 'summer destination' to 'a destination for all seasons and all reasons'. State is working on The Government of Himachal Pradesh in 2019 has launched Himachal Pradesh Tourism Policy-2019 focused to achieve Sustainable Development Goal (SDG)-8 and SDG 12 through tourism i.e. to achieve 'decent work and economic growth' and 'responsible consumption and production '. It will take tourism to country-side, unexplored areas through appropriate infrastructure (Himachal Tourism, 2019). According to IBEF (2020), tourism sector of Himachal Pradesh contributes to 6.6 per cent in the State GDP. There was 16.09 million domestic and 356,000 foreign tourists visited the state in 2018. There were 3,066 registered hotels in State. Jammu and Kashmir is promoting rural tourism to provide employment to the rural people who are dependent on agriculture for income. Jharkhand Tourism Policy 2015 to make Jharkhand most preferred destination both inside and outside India and develop tourism infrastructure.

Karnataka has a diverse flora fauna and cultural heritage including the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) World Heritage Karnataka is boosting private investment across the different tourism sectors through Karnataka Tourism Policy 2015 - 2020. The BBC travel survey has rated Kerala as most favorite destination among foreign travelers. Kerala has innovative tourism products to cater the leisure tourist. Kerala Tourism Policy 2017 is promoting the State as global brand for domestic as well as international tourists.

It was found that during budget of 2019-2020 Madhya Pradesh government allocated 229 crore for the development of State Tourism department. Tourism policy 2019 is promoting sustainable Tourism in the State for social economic development as well as a destination of complete tourism experiences. State government has

planned to make it a world class adventure, religious and heritage tourism destinations.

Maharashtra witnessed 119.2 million domestic tourists and 5.08 million foreign tourist arrival in 2015. Maharashtra Tourism Policy 2016 has the tourism as priority sector for economic growth. The State as also realised like other States that tourism is a tool to generate employment and sustainable development of Maharashtra. The policy proposed to generate 1 million additional jobs by 2025 in Maharashtra. The government has plan to generate 30000 crore for investment by 2025. Maharashtra government had proposed to generate employment through Micro Small Medium scale tourism units.

Manipur is a rich and prosperous in handicraft and handloom units. Manipur is described as 'flower on lofty heights', 'jewel of India' and 'Switzerland of East'. Manipur is blessed with nature and largest bamboo producing state in the country. Manipur tourism policy 2014 proposed to harness the tourism potential and attract tourism investment through to development of hotels, restaurants and heritage sites (Manipur Tourism Policy, 2014). The State of Meghalaya has witnessed the increase in number of tourists it was 839 363 in 2016 and it reached 1002907 in 2017 and generating employment. Mizoram is promoting eco-tourism through eco-tourism policy 2017 it is promoting value based tourism through conservation of wildlife nature and heritage. Government is developing tourism to generate employment opportunity for the people of the State. As per the draft tourism policy 2014 of Nagaland government, it has proposed to develop the tourism in the State through participation of private sector and have community welfare orientation. The government wants to reflect the real experience and identity of State through tourism policy and it will provide employment opportunity for women and youth.

Odisha government has launched Odisha tourism policy 2016 to promote sustainable tourism with a view to create employment opportunities and to bring about social economic benefits to the community.

The Government of Punjab has launched Tourism Policy 2018 with a paramount number of tourists to achieve from 25 million tourists in the State to 50 million by 2023. To achieve this purpose government has revolutionary plans to achieve infrastructure capable to handle projected tourists numbers. Rajasthan

Tourism policy 20 15 has plan to develop tourism projects within time frame. The policy is focused to develop existing infrastructure, and fostering income and employment. The policy is focused to impart employable skills through registered tourism units under the Department of Tourism in the State of Rajasthan.

Sikkim has launched Eco-tourism Policy 2011 to impart high quality learning experience for the tourists in the State. Sikkim launched Tourism Policy 2018 to achieve low impact sustainable Tourism. The development of tourism is among the top priority of the State. The policy has futuristic approach that provides employment and upcoming entrepreneurs spreading the benefits to the community at large whereas safeguarding the fragile ecosystem of the State. During 2016-17 the share of tourism in state GDP was 7.68 %. This policy has mentioned that tourism provides employment to a wider section of the society from construction to supplies. In addition, government stresses to provide employment to the local community through this tourism policy has planned long term sustainable employment and tourism is a key driver of the state economy. The policy is dedicated to ensure that Sikkim has the highest level of skills and capacity for quality service delivery through consistent human resource development. This policy is focused on maximizing employment opportunities for the locals. The tourism industry of Tamil Nadu has increased in terms of tourist arrival to reach 349.99 2 million in 2017. During 2018-19 state of Tamil Nadu witnessed top rank in context of receiving domestic as well as foreign tourists. One of the North-Eastern States of India i.e. Tripura has ancient places, temples, hills, biodiversity hotspots and wildlife sanctuaries. Tripura has promoted the state tourism in sustainable way through Eco-tourism Policy 2014. Tripura is improving safety and security for the tourists to increase the number of tourist in the state. Uttar Pradesh government has a plan to improve the basic facilities to increase the area of tourist interest through Tourism Policy in 2018. This policy is framed to attract an investment of 5,000 crore rupees every year to increase the footfall of domestic tourists by 15% and foreign tourists by 10%. The government has planned to develop road and air connectivity, so tourism can be promoted and more employment can be generated. One of the Himalayan States i.e. Uttarakhand launched Tourism Policy 2018 to ensure necessary basic services at all tourist destinations like parking toilet Automated Teller Machines (ATM), dispensaries, internet and telecommunication facilities. State government is promoting the tourism products

with competition to global destination by showcasing its spiritual, cultural and adventure tourism product. The policy proposed to achieve 0.5 million international tourists by 2022. West Bengal Tourism Policy-2016 is focused to increase the availability of branded hotel accommodation rooms in the State up to 100000 by 2020 and make tourism more sustainable. It can be inferred that employment generation, to larger share of tourist, economic development and infrastructure development are the major proposal of all the State tourism policies across the country. Whereas the leading tourism States along with unexplored and underdeveloped States of North-East India are focused towards sustainable development, community development and to enrich tourists' experiences while travelling to destinations of respective destinations. It was also investigated that the majority Indian States have vision to develop respective State as Global brand but unfortunately without have a plan to produce world class tourism professionals.

4.4 Tourism a Giant Source to Minimise Unemployment

According to Statista (2020), India's efficiency and productivity remained somewhat stagnant over the course of 3 or 4 years among Brazil, China and Russia. India also reported a rather large trade deficit over the past decade. Indian total exports fall behind its total amount of imports, essentially forcing the country to borrow money in order to finance the nation. This trade deficits have adverse impact on the developing/emerging economies as per the most economists. According to Furhmann (2020), the national unemployment rate is defined as the percentage of unemployed workers in the total labour force. It is widely recognized as a key indicator of the performance of a country's labour market. The Former Under-Secretary General of the United Nations i.e. Dr. Shashi Tharoor, during an interview to The Hindu (2018) had mentioned that there is need for investment in Indian tourism industry to overcome to deal with unemployment. Also, "the wonderful ruins around our country have remained ruins rather than becoming tourist sites. Tourism hires and employs 8 to 10 times as many people as any manufacturing industry can, that too skilled and unskilled people." Besides, it is clear that Indian tourism industry has a huge potential to generate employment. Hence, need to infuse strategy and planning among the tourism graduates; tourism professionals; policymakers;

academicians and other tourism industry stakeholders regarding tourism product development.

4.5 Contribution of Tourism in India

The role of Indian tourism industry is discussed below with regards employment, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), investment, government expenditure to facilitate tourism services, expenditure by domestic, business and leisure tourists as well as internal travel and tourism consumption.

a) Direct Contribution to Employment: The number of jobs generation directly in the travel and tourism sector. It is clear from the table that 2010 downwards till 2018 there is a growth in number of jobs (direct), percentage of employment and have positive growth employment in the country.

Table 4.2: Direct contribution to employment

Sr. No.	Year	000 of jobs	% of total employment	% growth
1.	2008	8994	2.0	7.0
2.	2009	8613	1.9	-4.2
3.	2010	9250	2.0	7.4
4.	2011	10365	2.2	12.0
5.	2012	11411	2.4	10.1
6.	2013	12704	2.6	11.3
7.	2014	14275	3.0	12.4
8.	2015	15970	3.3	11.9
9.	2016	16417	3.4	2.8
10.	2017	16909	3.5	3.0
11.	2018	17279	3.5	2.2

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

b) Total Contribution to Employment: The number of jobs generation directly in the travel and tourism sector adds the indirect and induced contribution. The table 4.3 shows that 2010 downwards till 2018 the tourism industry has a positive role in employment in direct and allied tourism industries. According to Okun Law, ‘a

country's GDP must grow at about a 4% rate for one year to achieve a 1% reduction in the rate of unemployment' (Furhmann, 2020).

Table 4.3: Total Contribution to Employment

Sr. No.	Year	000 of jobs	% growth	% of total employment
1.	2008	30418.5	2.18	6.63
2.	2009	30004.2	-1.36	6.54
3.	2010	29230.2	-2.58	6.31
4.	2011	29585.6	1.22	6.31
5.	2012	30243.1	2.22	6.34
6.	2013	30993.5	2.48	6.44
7.	2014	33462.1	7.96	6.94
8.	2015	35796	6.97	7.41
9.	2016	36562.3	2.14	7.55
10.	2017	37678.5	3.05	7.77
11.	2018	38565.5	2.35	7.89

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

c) Direct Contribution to GDP: GDP generated by industries that deals directly with tourists, including hotels, travel agents, airlines and other passenger transport services as well as the activities of restaurants and leisure industries that directly deal with tourists. It is equivalent to total internal travel and tourism spending (shown in table-4.13) with in a country less the purchases made by those industries (including imports). The direct contribution by tourism industry in GDP has a steady growth.

Table 4.4: Direct contribution to Indian GDP

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in billion (nominal)	Local currency in billion(real price)	% growth	% of GDP
1.	2008	1793.93	3130.11	5.18	3.29
2.	2009	1968.12	3298.85	5.39	3.29
3.	2010	2214.23	3366.74	2.06	3.04
4.	2011	2432.92	3407.21	1.20	2.87
5.	2012	2645.36	3433.64	0.78	2.74
6.	2013	2850.95	3467.90	1.00	2.62
7.	2014	3040.55	3536.85	1.99	2.49
8.	2015	3194.24	3636.14	2.81	2.38
9.	2016	3604.18	3995.94	9.90	2.42
10.	2017	3951.87	4206.17	5.26	2.38
11.	2018	4386.66	4489.37	6.73	2.36

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

d) Total Contribution to GDP: GDP generation directly by the travel and tourism sector adds its indirect and induced impacts. The tourism industry value chain is very large because it changes with type of tourism forms (Market Width, 2018).

Table 4.5: Total contribution to GDP

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in bl (nominal)	Local currency in bl (real price)	% growth	%share of GDP
1.	2008	5221.36	9110.42	6.10	9.58
2.	2009	5722.88	9592.36	5.29	9.57
3.	2010	6447.04	9802.72	2.193	8.86
4.	2011	7116.57	9966.47	1.67	8.39
5.	2012	7775.87	10093	1.27	8.07
6.	2013	8369.44	10180.6	0.87	7.68
7.	2014	8897.27	10349.5	1.66	7.29
8.	2015	9285.25	10569.8	2.13	6.93
9.	2016	10417.6	11550	9.27	6.99
10.	2017	11432.4	12168.1	5.35	6.89
11.	2018	12730.5	13028.6	7.07	6.84

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

e) Investment (capital investment): It includes capital investment spending by all industries directly involved in travel and tourism. This also contributes to investment spending by other industries on specific tourism assets such as new visitor accommodation and passenger transport equipment, as well as restaurant and leisure facilities for specific tourism use. It shows that investment from tourism value chain or non-tourism value chain companies are building or investing on infrastructure to facilitate tourism and it is in rise.

Table 4.6: Investment (Capital Investment)

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in bl (nominal)	Local currency in bl (real price)	% growth	% of total investment
1.	2008	1555.9	2714.79	173.03	8.15
2.	2009	1136.06	1904.2	-29.86	5.74
3.	2010	1318.21	2004.34	5.26	5.47
4.	2011	1545.34	2164.19	7.98	5.42
5.	2012	1756.95	2280.5	5.37	5.39
6.	2013	1949.46	2371.32	3.98	5.60
7.	2014	2126.7	2473.83	4.32	5.72
8.	2015	2318.67	2639.43	6.69	5.98
9.	2016	2382.01	2640.93	0.06	5.62
10.	2017	2587.03	2753.5	4.26	5.48
11.	2018	2990.56	3060.58	11.15	5.46

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

f) Government Individual Expenditures: Spending by government on travel and tourism services directly linked to visitor, such as cultural services (e.g. museum) or recreational services (e.g. National parks). The spending of government has crossed the one percent (of total government individual expenditure in 2018) to facilitate visitors.

Table 4.7: Indian Government individual expenditure

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in billion (nominal)	Local currency in billion(real price)	% growth	% share of total govt. individual expenditure
1.	2008	6.91	12.06	15.61	0.96
2.	2009	8.42	14.12	17.11	0.97
3.	2010	9.97	15.16	7.34	0.97
4.	2011	11.57	16.20	6.89	0.98
5.	2012	13.09	17.00	4.91	0.98
6.	2013	14.78	17.98	5.80	0.99
7.	2014	16.48	19.18	6.64	0.99
8.	2015	17.82	20.29	5.79	1.00
9.	2016	19.29	21.39	5.44	1.00
10.	2017	22.82	24.28	13.53	1.00
11.	2018	26.37	26.98	11.11	1.01

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

g). Domestic Tourism Spending: Spending within a country by that country's residence for both business and leisure trips. Multi use consumer durables are not included since they are not purchased solely for tourism purposes.

Table 4.8: Domestic Tourism Spending

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in billion (nominal)	Local currency in billion (real price)	% growth	%of whole economy GDP
1.	2008	4172.77	7280.79	5.93	7.64
2.	2009	4581.41	7679.1	5.45	7.65
3.	2010	5102.87	7758.91	1.03	7.00
4.	2011	5540.94	7759.86	0.00	6.52
5.	2012	5994.41	7780.67	0.26	6.20
6.	2013	6387.15	7769.32	-0.16	5.85
7.	2014	6711.48	7806.96	0.47	5.49

8.	2015	6963	7926.27	1.52	5.18
9.	2016	7810.75	8659.77	9.26	5.23
10.	2017	8462.21	9006.76	3.98	5.08
11.	2018	9423.93	9644.58	7.07	5.05

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

h) Outbound Travel and Tourism Expenditure: spending outside the country while residents on all trips abroad. The outbound spending is on rise and has .84 percent (2018) of national GDP. The increasing disposable income, decreasing cost of international airfare and availability of affordable travel packages are promoting the outbound travel (Economic Times, 2016). The increase in outbound tourism attracts the foreign nations' embassy, travel companies, hiring of tourism professionals without bound destination knowledge and establishment of cultural desk in country of origin.

Table 4.9: Outbound Tourism Expenditure

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in bl (nominal)	Local currency in bl (real price)	% growth	%share of total gdp
1.	2008	411.27	717.6	7.07	0.75
2.	2009	447.42	749.93	4.51	0.75
3.	2010	487.93	741.90	-1.07	0.67
4.	2011	664.37	930.43	25.41	0.78
5.	2012	664.58	862.62	-7.29	0.69
6.	2013	707.60	860.73	-0.22	0.65
7.	2014	921.81	1072.28	24.58	0.76
8.	2015	994.76	1132.37	5.60	0.74
9.	2016	1127.46	1250.01	10.39	0.76
10.	2017	1243.81	1323.85	5.91	0.75
11.	2018	1563.04	1599.64	20.83	0.84

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

i) Visitor exports (Foreign spending): Spending within the country by international tourists for both businesses and leisure trips, including spending on transport but excluding international spending on education. The percentage share of export has grown over the years and has reached 5.45 percent.

Table 4.10: Visitor Exports (foreign spending)

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in bl (nominal)	Local currency in bl (real price)	% growth	%share of export
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1.	2008	542.11	945.89	7.27	4.14
2.	2009	566.76	949.97	0.43	4.53
3.	2010	686.6	1043.98	9.90	4.37
4.	2011	844.24	1182.32	13.25	4.14
5.	2012	962.04	1248.72	5.62	4.01
6.	2013	1087.96	1323.39	5.98	4.01
7.	2014	1236.99	1438.9	8.73	4.22
8.	2015	1339.47	1524.77	5.97	4.91
9.	2016	1519.45	1684.61	10.48	5.31
10.	2017	1780.28	1894.84	12.48	5.63
11.	2018	1978.89	2025.22	6.88	5.45

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

j) Business Tourism Spending: Spending on business travel within a country by residence and international visitors.

Table 4.11: Business Tourism Spending

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in billion (nominal)	Local currency in billion (real price)	% growth	%share of GDP
1.	2008	336.27	586.74	5.84	0.235
2.	2009	238.64	400.00	-1.58	0.153
3.	2010	260.47	396.04	2.61	0.137
4.	2011	185.74	260.12	6.94	0.08
5.	2012	244.80	317.75	4.79	0.09
6.	2013	381.02	463.47	1.55	0.133
7.	2014	438.89	510.53	6.26	0.138
8.	2015	472.64	538.03	6.09	0.136
9.	2016	523.06	579.91	9.52	0.136
10.	2017	622.62	662.69	0.85	0.145
11.	2018	667.68	683.31	6.35	0.138

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

k) Leisure Tourism spending: A spending on leisure travel within a country by residents and international visitors. The growth rate of leisure tourism spending in 2008 was 6.08 percent and 3.05 percent of national GDP while it achieved a growth rate of 7.30 percent and GDP share reached at 2.21 percent in 2018.

Table 4.12: Leisure Tourism Spending

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in bl (nominal)	Local currency in bl (real price)	% growth	%share of GDP
1.	2008	4378.6	7639.94	6.08	3.05
2.	2009	4909.53	8229.07	7.71	3.13

3.	2010	5529	8406.84	2.16	2.90
4.	2011	6199.43	8682.06	3.27	2.78
5.	2012	6711.65	8711.64	0.34	2.64
6.	2013	7094.09	8629.25	-0.95	2.48
7.	2014	7509.59	8735.33	1.23	2.35
8.	2015	7829.82	8913.01	2.03	2.24
9.	2016	8807.14	9764.46	9.55	2.28
10.	2017	9619.87	10238.9	4.86	2.23
11.	2018	10735.1	10986.5	7.30	2.21

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

l) Internal Tourism and Travel Consumption: Total revenue generated with in a country by industries that deal directly with tourists including visitor exports, domestic spending and government individual spending. This does not include spending abroad by residents. The following table asserts that internal travel and tourism consumption is growing year by year.

Table 4.13: Internal Travel and Tourism Consumption

Sr. No.	Year	Local currency in billion (nominal)	Local currency in billion (real price)	% growth	%share of GDP
1.	2008	4714.87	8226.68	6.09	6.67
2.	2009	5148.17	8629.07	4.89	6.86
3.	2010	5789.47	8802.88	2.01	6.27
4.	2011	6385.18	8942.19	1.58	5.80
5.	2012	6956.45	9029.39	0.98	5.48
6.	2013	7475.11	9092.72	0.70	5.31
7.	2014	7948.48	9245.86	1.68	5.13
8.	2015	8302.46	9451.04	2.22	5.04
9.	2016	9330.2	10344.4	9.45	5.17
10.	2017	10242.5	10901.6	5.39	5.06
11.	2018	11402.8	11669.8	7.05	4.97

Source: WTTC Data Gateway

4.6 Conclusion

The Indian tourism industry has brought enormous benefits to the States and country. It is creating millions of jobs, protecting natural and cultural treasures, enhancing prosperity and reducing poverty. The Ministry of Tourism is promoting India as ‘The Land of Spirituality’, ‘land of sun, sea and surf’, ‘Rural India- True India’, ‘Land for modern travellers’ and ‘land of sustainable development’ so It won’t

be a surprise to rechristen India as ‘a country of many countries’. The punch line of India tourism can be replaced from Incredible India to ‘One visa =36 countries’.

The government has ambitious plans to make India the USD 5 trillion economy by 2024-25. The tourism industry is considered as a ‘champion’ to achieve this goal. Hence, it can be concluded that Indian tourism will have an important role to achieve the ‘biggest of the biggest’ size of Indian economy in future as well. All the State(s)/UT(s) across the country are putting continuum efforts to achieve a larger share of economic benefits. According to University Grant Commission, India has reported through its Skill Gap Report (2015) the huge skill gap in tourism industry as the expectations of employers and employees are different. The lack of soft skills, destination knowledge, poor negotiation and commercial management skills, inadequate knowledge of booking software as well as cultural understanding are major lacuna among the produced human resources in tourism industry. It is clear from above discussion that there is urgent need to reform Indian tourism education system because tourism industry is highly competitive and dynamic which demands human resource having competency to resolve real time problems as well to think out of the box.

The Ministry of Tourism is failed to establish National Tourism University even though it was planned to establish in 2015 (Business Standard, 2015) and proposed in National Tourism policy draft-2015 as well. This policy has a major goal to diversify the Indian tourism product, and to develop India as ‘must experience and revisiting destination’ and to produce ‘job creators instead of job seekers’ through tourism education. These goals are not achieved able in the dearth of holistic tourism education which is existing in the country at present (Singh and Singh, 2005; Dahiya, 2013; George, 2017 and Paliwal, 2017). It was mentioned by UNWTO (2002), the comprehensive tourism education leads to ‘development of destinations and tourism enterprises, customer loyalty and the compatibility of tourism with the natural environment and social development’. It is also found that existence of the same policy for decades as well as procedure of formulation of new policy is taking years in Indian context which reveals that there is lack of tourism experts in the government for policy formulation.

Tourism is one of the very important industries in the world and in India as well. Irrespective of the economies i.e. either developed, developing or under developing are promoting the tourism industry. The role and significance of tourism industry is very high for India because it contributes for myriad of benefits for overall growth of economy, motivates in preserving of natural resources. Tourism especially religious tourism can scale the Indian soft power through cultural diplomacy to new horizons. It can be extracted through competent tourism professionals, futuristic tourism policies, frequent change in tourism policies and key tourism posts must be held by tourism professionals as it is an era of knowledge based economy which demands specialisation based tourism education.

References

- Assumma, V., & Ventura, C. (2014). Role of cultural mapping within local development processes: A tool for the integrated enhancement of rural heritage. *Advanced Engineering Forum*, 11, 495-502.
- Bhonsale, M. (2019). Religious tourism as soft power: Strengthening India's outreach to Southeast Asia, 97. Observer Research Foundation. ISBN 978-93-89094-83-1.
- CVS. <http://www.cvs.edu.in/dep>. Accessed the 30th of April 2017, at 21:09.
- Dayananda, K. C., & Leelavathi, D. S. (2016). Evolution of tourism policy in India: An overview. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 21(12), 37-43.
- Economic Times. India's tourism sector may lose Rs 5 lakh cr, 4-5 cr jobs could be cut due to COVID-19. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/economy/indicators/indias-tourism-sector-may-lose-rs-5-lakh-cr-4-5-cr-jobs-could-be-cut-due-to-covid-19/articleshow/74968781.cms?from=mdr>. Accessed the 4th of April 2020, at 23:24.
- Economic Times. Outbound travel industry grows, but challenges remain. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/services/travel/outbound-travel-industry-grows-but-challenges-remain/articleshow/50926441.cms?from=mdr>. Accessed the 10th of August 2018, at 11:10.
- Fazili, A. I., Ali, S., & Khan, D. (2018). Tourist relative importance of factors influencing tourism development in J&K. *Journal of Management Research and Analysis*, 5(3), 342-347.

FICCI. The travel and hospitality industry are staring at a revenue loss of Rs.5 Trillion: Covid-19.<http://www.ficci.in/ficci-in-news-page.asp?nid=21674>. Accessed the 21st of April 2020, at 23:54.

Furhmann, R. (2020). <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/economics/12/okuns-law.asp>. Accessed the 22nd of April 2020, at 03:21.

Himachal Pradesh State Report. <https://www.ibef.org/states/himachal-pradesh.aspx>. Accessed the 1st of April 2020, 14:14.

Himachal tourism. <https://himachaltourism.gov.in>. Accessed the 27th September 2019, at 20:47.

Hindustan Times (2019). <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/a-record-over-24-crore-people-visited-kumbh-2019-more-than-total-tourists-in-up-in-2014-17/story-9uncpmhBPnBj11ClnTiYQP.html>. Accessed the 23rd of May 2019 at 09:09.

IBEF. <https://www.ibef.org/states/andhra-pradesh.aspx>. Accessed the 21st of April 2020, 14:14.

IHM Mumbai. <http://www.ihmctan.edu/the-institute.html>. Accessed the 18th of May 2019, at 23:12.

IITF.<https://iitf.gov.in/mod/scorm/player.php?a=23¤torg=&scoid=52&sesskey=da0zDICXFy&display=popup&mode=normal>. Accessed the 20th of January 2020 at 20:20.

King of Spain signals strong support for UNWTO's tourism ambitions. <https://www.unwto.org/king-of-spain-signals-strong-support-for-unwto-s-tourism-ambitions>. Accessed the 23rd of January 2020. At 21:40.

Livemint. <https://www.livemint.com/news/india/india-opens-up-137-mountain-peaks-for-mountaineering-trekking-1566532066895.html>. Accessed the 25th September 2019, at 04:07.

Make in India. <https://www.ibef.org/economy/make-in-india>. Accessed the 12th of May 2019. At 31:46.

- Market Width. What is tourism industry? <http://www.market-width.com/Tourism-Industry.htm>. Accessed the 24th of October 2018 at 13:57.
- Nagaland Tourism. https://tourism.nagaland.gov.in/?page_id=1145. Accessed the 23rd of January 2019 at 20:19.
- National tourism draft policy. http://tourism.gov.in/sites/default/files/policy/Draft_National_Tourism_Policy_2015.pdf. Accessed the 14th of March 2018, 13:13.
- National tourism policy 2002. <http://tourism.gov.in/sites/default/files/policy/National%20Tourism%20Policy%202002.pdf>. Accessed the 13th of July 2018 at 20:09.
- National Tourism University proposed at Noida. https://www.business-standard.com/article/pti-stories/national-tourism-university-proposed-at-noida-115032200681_1.html. Accessed the 23rd March 2018, 20:19.
- Paliwal, R. (2017). A study of gap analysis between tourism industry and tourism education in India. *International Journal of Current Research in Education, Culture and Society*, 1(1), 1-5.
- PIB (2020). Ministry of Tourism: Year-end review 2019. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseIframePage.aspx?PRID=1598374>. Accessed the 4th of January 2020, at 02:02.
- PIB. <https://pib.gov.in/Pressreleaseshare.aspx?PRID=1577036> Accessed the 12th of November, 2019, at 13:11.
- PIB. Ministry of Tourism: Year End Review 2019 <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseIframePage.aspx?PRID=1598374> Accessed the 4th January 2020, at 23:34.
- PIB. NMCM. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1592080>. Accessed the 19th November 2019, at 19:19.
- Sagarmala. Developing ports: Sagarmala Project. <https://www.makeinindia.com/article/-/v/developing-ports-sagarmala-project>. Accessed the 19th of October 2018, at 23:45.

Sikkim Tourism. http://sikkimtourism.gov.in/Webforms/General/pdf/Sikkim_Tourism_Policy_10.pdf. 23rd of January 2019 at 20:19

Skill Gap report. University Grant commission. <https://www.ugc.ac.in/skill/SectorReports.html>. Accessed the 15th of May 2018.

States. <https://www.ibef.org/states.aspx>. Accessed the 1st of April 2020, 14:14.

Statista. Unemployment rate in India 2019. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/271330/unemployment-rate-in-india/>. Accessed the 13th of February 2020, at 02:09.

Swadesh Darshan. <file:///E:/tourism%20books/Guidelines%20final.pdf>. Accessed the 12th of July 2019, at 20:20.

Swadeshdarshan. Ministry of tourism (2019). <http://swadeshdarshan.gov.in>. Accessed the 20th of December 2019, at 04:08.

Tamilnadu. <http://tourism.gov.in/sites/default/files/Other/India%20Tourism%20Statistics%20at%20a%20Glance%202019.pdf>. Accessed the 14th of November 2019 at 23:14.

The Hindu. India should tap tourism for jobs: Shashi Tharoor. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/india-should-tap-tourism-for-jobs-shashi-tharoor/article-25758289.ece>. Accessed the 17th of December 2018, at 03:34.

The key role of education in the new age of tourism: The WTO education council takes on new challenges. <https://www.hospitalitynet.org/news/4012371.html>. Accessed the 30th of June 2017, at 11:15.

Times of India. Now just pay \$25 for 30 days e-tourist visa in India during peak season. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/travel/destinations/now-just-pay-25-for-30-days-e-tourist-visa-in-india-during-peak-season/as70768525.cms>. Accessed the 1st of September 2019, at 04:09.

Tourism Satellite Account. <http://tourism.gov.in/sites/default/files/Other/011%20TSAI.pdf>. Accessed the 17th of November 2018, at 13:11.

UNWTO (2020). International tourist numbers could fall 60-80% in 2020
<https://www.unwto.org/news/covid-19-international-tourist-numbers-could-fall-60-80-in-2020>. Accessed the 8th of May 2020, at 23:45.

WTTC Data Gateway. <https://tool.wttc.org>. Accessed the 1st of April 2020. At 22:30.

WTTC. <https://wttc.org/Research/Economic-Impact>. Accessed the 2nd of April 2020.
At 21:30.